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ABSTRACTS

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Molecular modeling and docking studies of Plumbagin Derivatives against Cyclooxygenase-2

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Abstract: Pancreatic cancer has been researched to be the most lethal and aggressive form of cancer. Cyclooxygenase is one of the best drug targets to treat cancer. The enzyme cyclooxygenase is responsible for the formation of prostanooids, which are important mediators of inflammation and pain. COX 2 was chosen as a target for molecular docking, due to its existence as a significant cancer developer from literature reviews. The plumbagin was chosen as a ligand as it exhibited potent cytotoxicity against pancreatic cancer cells under nutrient-deprived conditions. The plumbagin derivatives 7e, 7f, 7g, 8a, 8b, 8c, 8d, 8e, 8f, 8g, 9a, 9b, 9c, 9d, 9e, 9f and 9g chosen based on SwissADME tool validation. The inhibitor site of the COX-2 was analyzed with Pymol to know the binding site of ligands. The amino acids were observed to be Asp-51, Pro-153, His-388, and Phe-381. Grid formation was done based on this location of the inhibitor site, and molecular docking was carried out using AutoDock Vina. The highest docking energy was observed as -7.4 Kcal/mol for 8d ligand against the target. The interactions within the complex were observed using Pymol and Discovery Studio. These complexes can be further analyzed by molecular dynamics studies to know the better binding affinities through free energy calculations.

Keywords: Pancreatic cancer, Cyclooxygenase-2, plumbagin derivative, molecular modeling and docking

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